

Building an interactive OER Tutorial for Early Career Researchers: Challenges at a micro Level

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ABSTRACT

Keywords

Case study, OER practice, CC licenses, Interactive learning materials, Academic Career Kit

Purpose of this paper

(1) Introduction

Difficulties with questions concerning copyright and ownership of online materials, and the fear of copyright infringement are among the main problems when it comes to offering and using OER in higher education (Harold & Rolfe, 2019; Hirsch, Baumann-Gibbon, & Rupprecht, 2016; Yawan & Ying, 2013). EconBiz (<https://www.econbiz.de/>) is a free search portal in economics and business studies. One of the aims of the portal is to foster research skills among students and early career researchers (ECR). When we started to provide online materials as OER we experienced these kinds of problems, especially at the micro level. Trying to offer our existing learning materials for students as OER – we met barriers and limitations in the fields of technical environments as well as on questions of re-using online materials. Thus we had some lessons learned, which we could use when building new projects, like the Academic Career Kit for ECR (<https://www.econbiz.de/eb/en/research-skills/academic-career-kit/>).

(2) OER Project / Best Practice

The aim was to build an *interactive* online tutorial that could be seamlessly integrated into third party online environments and which is *fully adaptable*. The tutorial in question addresses topics like:

- Publishing a first paper: Finding the right journal, considering open access, knowing your copyright as an author, and recognizing predatory journals,
- Metrics and Networking: Using social media in research to enhance your visibility and impact, measuring research impact with metrics and altmetrics, and
- Finding and sharing research data: benefits of sharing FAIR data, developing a data management plan, storing data in a data repository, CC licenses, etc.

To inspire learning, we considered it essential that the materials allow interaction; we wanted to offer elements of gamification and comic relief. In order to inspire re-use, we were well aware that not only the licenses, but also the technical environment must meet our requirements for easy re-use and adaption without the necessity of having a programmer at hand.

(3) Discussion

In our talk we want to discuss challenges of the development of interactive OER and present the questions, struggles, limitations, and answers that arose, when we developed the EconBiz Academic Career Kit. Among them are questions of re-use for special document types, like screenshots, logos, images, or videos, and the combination of materials with different licenses in one project, but also technical limitations and limitations to the findability and sharing of OER, that especially pertain to *interactive* OER materials.

Design/methodology/approach

Practice report / Case study.

Findings/expected Findings

Discussion of a best practice for the creation of an interactive OER tutorial

References

- Harold, S., & Rolfe, V. (2019). "I find the whole enterprise daunting": Staff understanding of Open Education initiatives within a UK university. *Open Praxis*, 11(1), 71-83. <https://doi.org/10.5944/openpraxis.11.1.918>
- Hirsch, N., Köpf, E., Baumann-Gibbon, O., & Rupprecht, C. (2016). *Praxisrahmen für Open Educational Resources (OER) in Deutschland*. Berlin: Wikimedia Deutschland e. V. <https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/4/4f/OER-Praxisrahmen.pdf>
- Yawan, L., & Ying, L. (2013). A Study on the Use of Open Educational Resources in China. In G. Dhanarajan & D. Porter (Ed.), *Open Educational Resources: An Asian Perspective* (pp. 21–39). Vancouver, British Columbia: Commonwealth of Learning and OER Asia.

https://oerknowledgecloud.org/sites/oerknowledgecloud.org/files/pub_PS_OER_Asia_web.pdf

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